

A Study of P16 Immunohistochemistry in Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma and Its Correlation with Human Papillomavirus16/18

Itisha Dhiman¹, Shailaja Shukla¹, Monisha Choudhary¹

Institution: Department of Pathology¹, Lady Hardinge medical college and Smt. Sucheta Kriplani Hospital, New Delhi

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 25-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Itisha Dhiman

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is considered an established causative agent of head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC). These HPV related tumors have a clinico-pathological profile that is different from non-HPV related tumors. The study was conducted to evaluate p16 over expression, HPV16/18 DNA detection and its correlation between various clinicopathological features and HPV.

Methods: Hundred patients with HNSCC were included in the study. p16 was evaluated using Immunohistochemistry (IHC) and was considered positive if $\geq 75\%$ of the tumor cells showed strong and diffuse nuclear/cytoplasmic staining. HPV 16/18 DNA was evaluated using Chromogenic in-situ Hybridization. Any brown colored dot like signal from the nucleus of the cell was considered positive. The results were analyzed using chi squared/Fisher exact test. The inter rater agreements between HPV-DNA and p16 expression was measured by calculating Cohen's kappa coefficient.

Results: p16 expression was seen in 41/100 HNSCC cases while HPV 16/18 DNA was detected in 20/100 cases. A statistically significant association was found between p16 expression and HPV16/18 detection ($P < 0.001$). p16 expression was most frequent in Oropharyngeal tumors which showed a significant association with p16 over expression ($P = 0.04$). The strength of agreement between HPV 16/18 DNA detection and p16 expression was moderate ($\kappa = 0.48$). p16 expression did not correlate with various other clinic-pathological parameters.

Conclusion: The present study supports the use of p16 IHC as a surrogate biomarker for HPV detection.

Keywords: Squamous cell carcinoma of head and neck, Papillomavirus, p16.

Key message: p16 as a surrogate marker for HPV16/18 DNA detection in HNSCC.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Each year, 300,000 cases of cancers of oral cavity and lip, 1,42,000 cases of pharyngeal cancer, 1,57,000 cases of laryngeal cancers and 87000 cases of rare nasopharyngeal cancer are diagnosed worldwide. [1] The incidence rates are higher in Indian subcontinent, Hongkong and Europe. [2] The association between high risk Human Papillomavirus (HR-HPV) and risk of oral cancer development was noted as far back as 1983. [3] Recently, it has been found that 15% - 20% of HNSCC are positive for HPV. [4-6] Among these 90-95% are positive for HR-HPV 16, HPV 18 in some cases and HPV type 31, 33 and 11 in considerably less cases. [4,5,7,8] Oropharyngeal squamous cell cancers (OPSCC) are more often associated with HPV. [9] It has been found that HR-HPV infection is an important etiological risk factor for the development of HNSCC in young patients. [8,9] It has been suggested in several studies that there is p16 oncoprotein over expression in HPV infection and hence, p16 can be used as a surrogate marker for active HPV

infection. [8,10-12] Moreover, recent studies have found that p16 expression itself is an indicator of survival outcomes in HNSCC patients regardless of tumor HPV status. [12] The present study was conducted to explore the association between p16 over expression, its correlation with various clinicopathological parameters and HPV status in the patients with HNSCC in Indian population, where we have a significantly higher incidence of oral cancers. [13]

Methods

Hundred cases of primary head and neck squamous cell cancer diagnosed by histology were included in the study. All patients with squamous cell carcinomas of lip and skin were excluded. Patients of carcinomas with recurrence of tumor and on treatment with radiotherapy and chemotherapy were excluded. Institute Ethical Committee clearance was obtained before the study was undertaken. An informed written consent was taken from all the patients. A detailed history and

examination findings were recorded in a predesigned performa. Lymph node involvement was assessed clinically. TNM staging was done for all the tumors according to AJCC criteria. The biopsy specimens were processed routinely, Haematoxylin and Eosin stained sections were examined. They were graded by using World Health Organization criteria. [14]

p16 Immunohistochemistry (IHC): p16 was evaluated using monoclonal antibody raised against p16 using the CINtec® Histology Kit. Sections of 5 µm were deparaffinized with xylene and rehydrated with graded alcohols. Antigen epitopes were unmasked by keeping the slides in staining jars filled with epitope retrieval solution and were kept in a decloaking chamber at 95 - 99°C for 30 minutes. The slides were kept in a moist chamber and 100 µl peroxidase blocking reagent was applied to block the other antigenic sites. Primary antibody (Mouse Anti-Human p16INK4a) was applied and incubated for 30 minutes subsequently visualization reagent was added and incubated for 30 minutes. Substrate chromogen Solution was added for visualization of reaction. Counterstaining was done with hematoxylin. p16 was considered positive if $\geq 75\%$ of cells showed nuclear and cytoplasmic expression.

HPV16/18 Chromogenic In Situ Hybridization (CISH): Formalin fixed and paraffin-embedded sections were evaluated for HPV 16/18 using CISH (Zytovision, Germany). Sections of 5 µm thickness were incubated at 70°C, dewaxed in xylene and rehydrated in graded alcohol. Slides were incubated in 3% H₂O₂. Pepsin solution was applied and slides were incubated for 10 minutes at 37°C in a humidity chamber. Heat pretreatment solution was preheated in a water bath at 95°C. Slides were placed in prewarmed heat pre-treatment solution EDTA at 95°C for 15 minutes. 10 µl of HPV 16/18 probes were pipetted onto each sample. The samples were then denatured at 75°C for 5 minutes and then hybridized at 37°C for 60 minutes in a hybridization chamber. This was followed by serial application of mouse-anti-DIG, anti-mouse-HRP-polymer for 30 minutes at 37°C. Slides were washed and diaminobenzidine chromogen was applied. Slides were counterstained using nuclear blue solution. Evaluation was carried out under light microscope. Any brown colored dot like signal from the nucleus of the cell was considered positive.

Statistical Analysis: Data between the groups were compared using Chi-squared test or Fisher's exact test as appropriate. P value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The inter rater agreements between HPV-DNA presence and p16 expression was measured by calculating Cohen's kappa coefficient (κ). A κ - value <0.20 was considered slight agreement, 0.21-0.40 as fair,

0.41-0.60 as moderate, 0.61-0.80 as good and 0.81-0.99 as excellent agreement.

Results

Hundred cases of HNSCC confirmed by histology were included in the study. The various clinicopathological parameters of 100 cases and their association with p16 expression are given in Table 1. p16 expression was found in 41% while remaining 59% cases were p16 negative.

It was observed that among 41% p16 positive patients 63.4 % patients were >50 years of age while 36.6 % were < 50 years of age ($P=0.67$). Overall p16 expression was found more commonly in women i.e. 52.4% as compared to men (52.4% and 38% respectively, $P=0.31$). Among p16 positive cases 61% patients were non tobacco chewers while 39 % were habitual tobacco chewers ($P=0.41$). p16 positivity was seen in 61% patients with no history of betel nut chewing which reduced to 39% who had such history($P=0.39$). p16 positivity was seen in 80.5% patients who were smokers as compared 19.5% patients who were non smokers ($P=0.59$). Out of 41% p16 positive patients 58.5% patients did not consume alcohol which reduced to 41.5% in patients who consumed alcohol ($P=0.83$). Since only one out of 100 patients gave sexual history, no association between 16 expression and sexual history could be established. Overall, p16 expression was more commonly seen in oropharyngeal tumors 57% as compared to tumors located in non-oropharyngeal sites i.e. 34.7% , the association was significant ($P=0.04$). Most common tumor subsite for p16 expression was soft palate (75%) followed by base of tongue (61.5%) and (33.3%) in tonsils ($P=0.23$). All p16 positive tumors (41%) were in early T stage i.e. T1+T2, none of the tumors in T3 and T4 stage were p16 positive ($P=0.26$). When the cutoff was 2cm, 44.4% of small tumors expressed p16 and 38.4% large tumors showed p16 expression ($P=0.66$). P16 expression was seen in 42.1% patients with lymphadenopathy which reduced to 40.3% patients without lymphadenopathy ($P=1.00$). Maximum p16 expression was seen in 34.2% cases of stage I disease as compared to other stages ($P=0.78$).p16 expression was seen in 40.7% patients with grade 1 tumors, and in 38.6% patients with grade 2 tumors. Grade 3 tumors showed p16 expression in 100% cases ($P=0.22$).

HPV 16/18 DNA was detected in 20 % cases of HNSCC. Among 41% p16 positive cases 46.3% were HPV16/18 DNA positive while 53.6% were HPV 16/18 DNA negative. One HPV 16/18 DNA positive case did not express p16. There was a significant association between p16 expression and HPV DNA status ($P<0.001$). Table 2

The overall sensitivity of p16 expression was 95% and overall specificity was 72.5% as shown in

Table 2. A moderate agreement was observed for HPV 16/18 DNA detection and p16 expression (k=0.48).

Table1: Demographic characteristics of 100 patients of HNSCC and their correlation with p16 expression

Patient /Tumor characteristics (n=100)		Number of cases	P16 positive (n=41)	P16 negative (n=59)	P-value
Age(years)	<50	40	15	25	0.679
	≥ 50 yrs	60	26	34	
Gender	Men	79	30	49	0.318
	Women	21	11	10	
Smoking	Present	83	33	50	0.598
	Absent	17	8	9	
Tobacco chewers	Present	45	16	29	0.414
	Absent	55	25	30	
Alcohol	Present	43	17	26	0.839
	Absent	57	24	33	
Betel nut/Pan chewing	Present	34	16	18	0.398
	Absent	66	25	41	
Tumor Site	Oropharynx	28	16	12	0.04
	Non-Oropharynx	72	25	47	
Tumor Subsite	Base of tongue	18	11	7	0.23
	Tonsil	6	2	4	
	Soft palate	4	3	1	
	Others	72	25	47	
Tumor size(cm)	<2	45	20	25	0.660
	>2	39	15	24	
	Not determined	16			
T stage	T1+T2	97	41	56	0.267
	T3+T4	3	0	3	
Clinical stage	Stage I&II	60	25	35	1.000
	Stage III&IV	40	16	24	
Histological grade	Grade 1	54	22	32	0.225
	Grade 2	44	17	27	
	Grade 3	02	2	0	
HPV16/18	Positive	20	19	1	0.01
	Negative	80	22	58	

Table 2: Sensitivity, Specificity and NPV of p16 in detecting underlying HPV infection.

HPV status	P16 positive	P16 negative	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
HPV positive	19	1	95%	72.5%	46.3%	98.3%
HPV negative	22	58				

Table 3: Comparison of association between p16 expression and oropharynx in this study with other studies.

Study	P16 expression in oropharynx	P value
Ralli et al [17]	80.7%	0.33
Stephen et al [18]	65%	<0.001
Deng et al [19]	80%	<0.002
Salazar et al [20]	53%	<0.01
Zhao et al [22]	77.8%	<0.001
Sannigrahi et al [23]	42.8%	NS
Singhi et al [24]	88%	<0.001
Present study	57.1%	0.04

Figure 1: Photomicrograph showing well differentiated squamous cell carcinoma, (H&E,100x)

Figure 2: Photomicrograph showing diffuse strong cytoplasmic/nuclear p16 overexpression (IHC,100x)

Figure 3: HPV16/18 DNA detection by Chromogenic In Situ Hybridization (CISH, 400X)

Discussion

The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has recognized genotype HPV 16 as a

cause for OPSCC. [15] Among the OPSCC that have tested HPV positive, the rates are highest in tonsillar cancer. [4, 16]

In contrast to other studies [11] there was no association between p16 expression and younger age group, in our study 63.4% p16 positive patients were >50 years of age, however similar results were reported by Ralli et al. [17] It was observed that p16 expression in HNSCC was more frequent in women as compared to men (52.4% and 38% respectively). Dahlstrand et al [11], Stephen et al [18] and Deng et al [19] reported that p16 expression was higher in women i.e. 75%, 36% and 26.1% respectively as compared to men. Similar to other studies [17, 20] it was found that 58.5% patients with p16 expression were more likely to have no history of alcohol consumption. Iyer et al [21] found that p16 expression was significantly higher in non drinkers (P=0.01). In accordance with other studies [21] p16 expression was more common in patients with no history of betel nut/pan chewing and who were non tobacco chewers (61% each). Among smokers and non smoker patients, p16 expression was more in smokers (80.5%); this is in contrast to other studies which saw p16 expression in patients who were non smokers. [18, 19] In the present study, only 1 out of 100 patients gave history of multiple sexual partners. This can be attributed to social and cultural differences or small number of patients providing such history. p16 expression was seen in 57.1% tumors and were significantly different between oropharyngeal and non-oropharyngeal sites(P=0.04) this is in accordance to many authors [17-20, 22-24] as shown in Table 3. Among individual subsites, p16 expression was more frequently seen in base of tongue SCC's this is in contradiction to most other studies which have found higher p16 expression in tonsillar SCC's. [4, 16, 21] All lower T stage tumors (T1+T2) showed p16 expression while none of the cases in T3+T4 group expressed p16. Iyer et al [21] reported a significant correlation between higher p16 expression in lower T stage tumors (P=0.03). On the contrary, Kawakami et al[30], Zhao et al[22], Salazar et al[20], Sannigrahi et al[23] found no association. As reported in previous studies[20] p16 expression was found in 61% cases with early stage (stage I&II) and 39% cases with late stage (stage III&IV) HNSCC. However, the difference was not significant. In the present study, p16 expression was seen in 61% patients without lymphadenopathy. There was no association between p16 expression and lymph node status. Similar to the present study it was observed that p16 positive cases were more likely to have lower N stage i.e. N0-N1; however the difference was not statistically significant. [19] Ralli et al [17] reported that 82.8 % p16 positive cases were lymph node negative (P=0.03). On the contrary, few authors reported that p16 positive patients were more likely to have higher N stage and the association was significant (P=0.004, P=0.02, respectively). [20, 22] In the present study,

p16 expression was seen in 40.7% patients with grade 1 tumors and in 38.7% patients with grade 2 tumors. Interestingly, p16 expression was seen in 100% patients with grade 3 tumors but the number was too small (only 2 case). However, no association was found between histological grade and p16 expression. Dahlstrand et al [11] reported 55% grade 3 tumors expressing p16, but association with histological grade was not significant. In the literature there have been conflicting studies regarding p16 expression and tumor grade as p16 expression is seen both in well and poorly differentiated SCC(P= 0.03 and p<0.001, respectively). [19, 21]

p16 expression was seen in 19/20 HPV16/18 DNA positive cases. There was a significant association between p16 expression and HPV DNA status (P<0.001). This was in concordance with other studies. [11, 24, 26-32] In the present study, among 41% p16 positive patients, HPV was detected only in 19 cases. There were 22(53.6%) discrepant cases which were HPV16/18 DNA negative and p16 positive. In the literature, about 30% tumors have been found to be HPV DNA negative and p16 positive. [12] This discrepancy can be observed due to many reasons including sensitivity of the technique used, presence of other HPV types other than 16/18 and over expression of p16 by other mechanisms. Currently, combinations of various tests are being used for HPV detection, IHC and ISH being low sensitive methods and PCR detection, a high sensitivity technique. Authors have reported higher HPV detection rates in HNSCC using PCR technique. [18, 33-35] Another study detected HPV DNA in 49% patients using PCR while using ISH only 20% tumors were found to be HPV DNA positive. [11] The latter figure is the same as in the present study. However few authors have reported detection rates almost similar to the HPV detection rate by PCR. [12, 24, 31] There was one discrepant case which was HPV 16/18 DNA positive but did not express p16. p16 negative and HPV positive tumors are rare. It has been suggested that in patients with history of smoking, alcohol consumption and intake of betel quid, p16 can be lost via genetic or epigenetic changes which may lead to absent or decreased p16 expression. [17, 22] In the present study, the sensitivity of p16 expression as a surrogate marker for HPV 16/18 detection was 95% and overall specificity was 72.5%. This is in accordance to many authors. [11, 19, 24, 34] Since, sensitivity of p16 IHC in detecting HPV16/18 infection (which account for >90% of HPV associated HNSCC) is 95%; it can safely be assumed that p16 testing can be used as a surrogate marker for HPV infection. In the present study, the strength of agreement between HPV 16/18 DNA and p16 expression was moderate similar findings were reported by Salazar et al. [20]

Conclusions

p16 IHC must be performed on all HNSCC cases as it is simple, cost effective and easy to perform. p16 can be used as a surrogate marker for HPV detection in HNSCC. The less specificity of p16 advocates the use of an additional HPV specific test such as PCR, ISH, E6/E7 mRNA expression or a combination of these tests. HPV DNA testing for types 16 & 18 may be undertaken as these 2 types are involved in >90% cases of HNSCC. Although, ISH/CISH is a less sensitive method but the approach is practical and can be readily implemented in most of the laboratories as compared to PCR so it can be used as a method of choice in resource poor laboratories. PCR technique can be reserved for the p16 positive and HPV 16/18 DNA negative cases on ISH/CISH. HPV16/18 DNA negative cases should be subjected to testing with more extended panel of HPV type specific probes. p16 IHC can be used to gain prognostic information independent of HPV status of HNSCC.

References

1. Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, Rebelo M *et al.* Cancer incidence and mortality worldwide: Sources, methods and major patterns in GLOBOCAN 2012. *Int J Cancer* 2015;136:E359-86.
2. Sankaranarayanan R, Masuyer E, Swaminathan R, Ferlay J, Whelan S. Head and neck cancer: a global perspective on epidemiology and prognosis. *Anticancer Res* 1998;18:4779-86.
3. Syrjänen K, Syrjänen S, Lamberg M, Pyrhönen S, Nuutinen J. Morphological and immunohistochemical evidence suggesting human papillomavirus (HPV) involvement in oral squamous cell carcinogenesis. *Int J Oral Surg* 1983;12:418-24.
4. Gillison ML, Koch WM, Capone RB, Spafford M, Westra WH, Wu L *et al.* Evidence for a causal association between human papillomavirus and a subset of head and neck cancers. *J Natl Cancer Inst* 2000;92:709-20.
5. Hafkamp HC, Speel EJ, Haesevoets A, Bot FJ, Dinjens WN, Ramaekers FC *et al.* A subset of head and neck squamous cell carcinomas exhibits integration of HPV 16/18 DNA and overexpression of p16INK4A and p53 in the absence of mutations in p53 exons 5-8. *Int J Cancer* 2003;107:394-400.
6. Hafkamp HC, Manni JJ, Speel EJ. Role of human papillomavirus in the development of head and neck squamous cell carcinomas. *Acta Otolaryngol* 2004;124:520-26.
7. Näsman A, Attner P, Hammarstedt L, Du J, Eriksson M, Giraud G *et al.* Incidence of human papillomavirus (HPV) positive tonsillar carcinoma in Stockholm, Sweden: an epidemic of viral-induced carcinoma?. *Int J Cancer* 2009;125:362-66.
8. van Monsjou HS, van Velthuysen ML, van den Brekel MW, Jordanova ES, Melief CJ, Balm AJ. Human papillomavirus status in young patients with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma. *Int J Cancer* 2012;130:1806-12.
9. Ringström E, Peters E, Hasegawa M, Posner M, Liu M, Kelsey K. Human papillomavirus type 16 and squamous cell carcinoma of the head and neck. *Clin Cancer Res* 2002;8:3187-92.
10. Lewis JS Jr. p16 Immunohistochemistry as a standalone test for risk stratification in oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma. *Head Neck Pathol* 2012;6:S75-82.
11. Mellin Dahlstrand H, Lindquist D, Björnestrål L, Ohlsson A, Dalianis T, Munck-Wikland E *et al.* P16(INK4a) correlates to human papillomavirus presence, response to radiotherapy and clinical outcome in tonsillar carcinoma. *Anticancer Res* 2005;25:4375-83.
12. Lewis JS Jr, Thorstad WL, Chernock RD, Haughey BH, Yip JH, Zhang Q *et al.* p16 Positive oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma: an entity with a favorable prognosis regardless of tumor HPV status. *Am J Surg Pathol* 2010;34:1088-96.
13. Takiar R, Nadayil D, Nandakumar A. Projections of number of cancer cases in India (2010-2020) by cancer groups. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev* 2010;11:1045-49.
14. Barnes EL, Verbin RS, Guggenheimer J. Cancer of the oral cavity and oropharynx. In: Barnes L, editor. *Surgical Pathology of the Head and Neck*, 2nd ed. New York:Marcel Dekker Inc.;2001.p.369-438.
15. IARC Working Group on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans. Biological agents. Volume 100 B. A review of human carcinogens. *IARC Monogr Eval Carcinog Risks Hum.* 2012;100(Pt B):1-441.
16. Strome SE, Savva A, Brissett AE, Gostout BS, Lewis J, Clayton AC *et al.* Squamous cell carcinoma of the tonsils: a molecular analysis of HPV associations. *Clin Cancer Res* 2002;8:1093-1100.
17. Ralli M, Singh S, Yadav SP, Sharma N, Verma R, Sen R. Assessment and clinicopathological correlation of p16 expression in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma. *J Can Res Ther* 2016;12:232-37.
18. Stephen JK, Divine G, Chen KM, Chitale D, Havard S, Worsham MJ. Significance of p16 in site-specific HPV positive and HPV negative Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma. *Cancer Clin Oncol* 2013;2:51-61.
19. Deng Z, Hasegawa M, Aoki K, Matayoshi S, Kiyuna A, Yamashita Y *et al.* A comprehensive evaluation of human papillomavirus posi-

- tive status and p16INK4a overexpression as a prognostic biomarker in head and neck squamous cell carcinoma. *Int J Oncol* 2014;45:67-76.
20. Salazar CR, Anayannis N, Smith RV, Wang Y, Haigentz M Jr, Garg M *et al.* Combined P16 and human papillomavirus testing predicts head and neck cancer survival. *Int J Cancer* 2014;135:2404-12.
 21. Iyer NG, Dogan S, Palmer F, Rahmati R, Nixon IJ, Lee N *et al.* Detailed Analysis of Clinicopathologic Factors Demonstrate Distinct Difference in Outcome and Prognostic Factors Between Surgically Treated HPV-Positive and Negative Oropharyngeal Cancer. *Ann Surg Oncol* 2015;22:4411-21.
 22. Zhao N, Ang MK, Yin XY, Patel MR, Fritchie K, Thorne L *et al.* Different cellular p16INK4a localisation may signal different survival outcomes in head and neck cancer. *Br J Cancer* 2012 Jul 24;107(3):482-490. doi: 10.1038/bjc.2012.264. Epub 2012 Jun 26.
 23. Sannigrahi MK, Singh V, Sharma R, Panda NK, Radotra BD, Khullar M. Detection of active human papilloma virus-16 in head and neck cancers of Asian North Indian patients. *Oral Dis* 2016;22:62-68.
 24. Singhi AD, Westra WH. Comparison of human papillomavirus in situ hybridization and p16 immunohistochemistry in the detection of human papillomavirus-associated head and neck cancer based on a prospective clinical experience. *Cancer* 2010;116:2166-73.
 25. Wang F, Zhang H, Xue Y, Wen J, Zhou J, Yang X *et al.* A systematic investigation of the association between HPV and the clinicopathological parameters and prognosis of oral and oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinomas. *Cancer Med* 2017;6(5):910-17.
 26. Riener MO, Hoegel J, Iro H, Hartmann A, Agaimy A. IMP3 and p16 expression in squamous cell carcinoma of the head and neck: A comparative immunohistochemical analysis. *Oncol Lett* 2017;14(2):1665-70.
 27. Meng HX, Miao SS, Chen K, Li HN, Yao G, Geng J *et al.* Association of p16 as Prognostic Factors for Oropharyngeal Cancer: Evaluation of p16 in 1470 Patients for a 16 Year Study in Northeast China. *Biomed Res Int* 2018;2018:9594568.
 28. Nopmaneepaisarn T, Tangjaturonrasme N, Rawangban W, Vinayanuwattikun C, Keelawat S, Bychkov A. Low prevalence of p16-positive HPV-related head-neck cancers in Thailand: tertiary referral center experience. *BMC Cancer* 2019;19(1):1050.
 29. Chen TC, Wu CT, Ko JY, Yang TL, Lou PJ, Wang CP *et al.* Clinical characteristics and treatment outcome of oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma in an endemic betel quid region. *Sci Rep* 2020;10(1):526.
 30. Kawakami H, Okamoto I, Terao K, Sakai K, Suzuki M, Ueda S *et al.* Human papillomavirus DNA and p16 expression in Japanese patients with oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma. *Cancer Med* 2013; 2:933-41.
 31. Fakhry C, Westra WH, Li S, Cmelak A, Ridge JA, Pinto H *et al.* Improved survival of patients with human papillomavirus-positive head and neck squamous cell carcinoma in a prospective clinical trial. *J Natl Cancer Inst* 2008;100:261-69.
 32. Jitani AK, Raphael V, Mishra J, Shunyu NB, Khonglah Y, Medhi J. Analysis of Human Papilloma Virus 16/18 DNA and its Correlation with p16 Expression in Oral Cavity Squamous Cell Carcinoma in North-Eastern India: A Chromogenic in-situ Hybridization Based Study. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2015;9:EC04-07.
 33. Balaram P, Nalinakumar KR, Abraham E, Balan A, Hareendran NK, Bernard HU *et al.* Human papillomaviruses in 91 oral cancers from indian betel quid chewers—high prevalence and multiplicity of infections. *Int J Cancer*. 1995 May 16;61(4):450-54.
 34. Rotnáglová E, Tachezy R, Saláková M, Procházka B, Košl'abová E, Veselá E *et al.* HPV involvement in tonsillar cancer: prognostic significance and clinically relevant markers. *Int J Cancer* 2011;129:101-10.
 35. Donà MG, Spriano G, Pichi B, Rollo F, Laquintana V, Covello R *et al.* Human papillomavirus infection and p16 overexpression in oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma: a case series from 2010 to 2014. *Future Microbiol* 2015;10:1283-91.